

ACTIVE GASTRITIS IN HELICOBACTER PYLORI ASSOCIATED PEPTIC ULCER DISEASE IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL OF RAWALPINDI

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Background: Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) remains a major global health problem. Data from Pakistan on the histopathological spectrum of gastritis in relation to clinical risk factors remain limited.

Objective: Evaluation of demographic, clinical, and histopathological characteristics of patients with PUD and determine associations with active gastritis.

Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi, over six months from August 2024 to January 2025. Ninety-five patients with endoscopically diagnosed PUD were included through consecutive sampling. Gastric antral biopsies were obtained and examined using hematoxylin & eosin and Giemsa staining.

Results: Duodenal ulcers were most common (44.2%), followed by gastric (35.8%) and esophageal (20.0%). Active gastritis was observed in 54.7% of patients, while chronic inflammation was present in 68.4%. Active gastritis was significantly associated with male gender (72.7%, $p=0.021$), younger age (≤ 40 years: 85.0%, $p<0.001$), low socioeconomic status (70.0%, $p=0.033$), NSAID intake (78.9%, $p=0.012$), smoking (73.5%, $p=0.018$), and family history of PUD (85.7%, $p=0.005$).

INTRODUCTION

Global health issues related to PUD-associated gastritis are a cause of morbidity and mortality. Four million people worldwide suffer with peptic ulcer disease (PUD), which has an estimated yearly incidence of 0.1 to 0.3%¹. About 10% of adults in the United States throughout the first half of the 20th century suffered with PUD. Numerous studies carried out in the previous 20–30 years showed a substantial decline in the

prevalence of PUD. These trends were attributed to the application of new anti-PUD medicines as well as improved sanitation, hygiene, and the prudent use of NSAIDs^{2,3}. Studies from Asia show high prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* infection, while exposure rates in Pakistan increase with age and socioeconomic status^{4,5}. Gram-negative, urease-positive, spiral-shaped *Helicobacter pylori* bacteria cause inflammation in

the underlying gastric mucosa, which can result in acute gastritis, chronic gastritis, or both⁵. More than 50% of people globally are afflicted by this most prevalent bacterial infection, while only 1-3% of cases are reported. This infection remains lifetime in cases of carelessness in diagnosis and treatment, carrying a 15% risk of PUD, a 2% risk of stomach adenocarcinomas, and a 2% risk of MALT lymphoma^{6,7}. The third most common cause of cancer-related fatalities worldwide in 2020 was *H. pylori*-related disease, accounting for almost a million new cases of stomach cancer and about 800,000 deaths. There were an estimated 4.4 billion *H. pylori* infected individuals globally in 2015, with the frequency of the infection ranging greatly from 18.9% to 87.7%⁸.

Acute infection with *Helicobacter pylori* often remains undiagnosed because it usually presents with subtle or nonspecific symptoms. The current gold standard for identifying *H. pylori* infection and determining its histopathological pattern (active versus chronic) as well as the location of mucosal damage (antrum or corpus) is esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) combined with gastric biopsy^{7,9}.

When *H. pylori* persist, it leads to chronic gastritis of varying degrees, most commonly an antral-predominant pattern¹⁰. Prolonged inflammation eventually causes destruction of parietal cells, resulting in hypochlorhydria and the development of atrophic gastritis and intestinal metaplasia, both recognized as precancerous changes. Histologically, active gastritis is identified by the presence of neutrophilic infiltration within a chronically inflamed mucosa. Neutrophils respond most rapidly to eradication therapy, whereas eosinophils decline afterward, and lymphocytes and plasma cells usually regress more slowly¹⁰.

A descriptive cross-sectional study conducted at a tertiary care hospital in western Nepal among dyspeptic patients reported chronic gastritis in 60% of cases. Furthermore, *H. pylori* infection of mild, moderate, and severe grades was documented in 59.32%, 65.38%, and 76.92% of patients, respectively⁷.

Timely recognition of *H. pylori*-associated active gastritis using advanced diagnostic approaches can offer therapeutic advantages and help reduce complications by halting disease progression. Gastritis remains a prevalent condition in the Pakistani population, and performing endoscopy with targeted biopsies may assist in early diagnosis. However, local data on the prevalence of *H. pylori* infection and its correlation with the histopathological spectrum of chronic gastritis remain limited.

METHODOLOGY:

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the Gastroenterology and Pathology Departments of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi, over a period of six months from August 2024 to January 2025. A sample size of 95 was calculated using the WHO sample size calculator, based on a 95% confidence level, an anticipated prevalence of chronic *Helicobacter pylori* infection among patients with peptic ulcer disease (PUD) of 60%,⁷ and an absolute precision of 10%. Participants were recruited through consecutive non-probability sampling. The inclusion criteria comprised patients of either gender, aged 12–81 years, who were diagnosed with PUD via upper gastrointestinal (UGI) endoscopy and confirmed by gastric biopsy. Patients with a history of *H. pylori* eradication therapy within the preceding month or those with neoplastic lesions were excluded from the study. Data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire, clinical evaluation, laboratory investigations, and endoscopic findings. Sociodemographic details, including age, gender, socioeconomic status, smoking habits, and NSAID use, were recorded alongside comprehensive medical history. UGI endoscopy was performed in all patients, and gastric antral biopsies were obtained. Specimens were fixed in 10% formalin, processed, and sectioned at a thickness of 3–4 μm . Two sets of slides were prepared per sample: one stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) for histomorphological assessment, and the other with Giemsa for detection of *H. pylori*. All slides were examined by a single experienced

pathologist under light microscopy. Positive biopsies were further evaluated for active gastritis (presence of neutrophilic infiltration), chronic gastritis, intestinal metaplasia, dysplasia, or malignancy. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20.0.

RESULT

A total of 95 patients with peptic ulcer disease (PUD) were included in this study. The mean age of the participants was 45.0 ± 20.8 years (range 12–76 years). More than half of the patients were male (57.9%) while females constituted 42.1%. In terms of socioeconomic status, 45.3% of patients belonged to the low-income group, 41.1% to the middle-income group, and only 13.6% to the high-income group (Table 1).

With respect to ulcer type, duodenal ulcer was the most common (44.2%), followed by gastric ulcer (35.8%) and esophageal ulcer (20.0%). A

history of NSAID intake was present in 40.0% of cases, while 35.8% of patients reported a positive smoking history (Table 2). Chronic inflammation was more frequent, being present in 68.4% of the cases (Table 3).

Active gastritis was significantly more common in males (72.7%) than females (30.0%) ($p = 0.021$). Younger patients (≤ 40 years) had a markedly higher prevalence (85.0%) compared to those > 40 years (32.7%) ($p < 0.001$). Patients from low socioeconomic status showed the highest rate (70.0%) compared to middle (51.3%) and high (26.7%) groups ($p = 0.033$) (Table 4).

Among clinical factors, NSAID users had a higher prevalence of active gastritis (78.9%) than non-users (38.6%) ($p = 0.012$). Smokers were more affected (73.5%) than non-smokers (44.3%) ($p = 0.018$). Family history of peptic ulcer disease was strongly associated, with 85.7% showing active gastritis versus 46.0% without such history ($p = 0.005$) (Table 5).

Variable	Categories	Frequency (%)
Age (years)	Mean \pm SD	45.0 ± 20.8 (Range 12–76)
Gender	Male	55 (57.9%)
	Female	40 (42.1%)
Socioeconomic Status	Low	43 (45.3%)
	Middle	39 (41.1%)
	High	13 (13.6%)

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of patients (n = 95).

Variable	Categories	Frequency (%)
PUD Type	Gastric ulcer	34 (35.8%)
	Duodenal ulcer	42 (44.2%)
	Esophageal ulcer	19 (20.0%)
NSAID Intake	Yes	38 (40.0%)
	No	57 (60.0%)
Smoking History	Yes	34 (35.8%)
	No	61 (64.2%)

Table 2: Clinical profile of patients with peptic ulcer disease.

Variable	Categories	Frequency (%)
Number of biopsy fragments	Mean \pm SD	3 \pm 1 (Range 1-6)
Active Gastritis	Present	52 (54.7%)
	Absent	43 (45.3%)
Chronic Inflammation	Present	65 (68.4%)
	Absent	30 (31.6%)

Table 3: Histopathological findings in biopsy specimens of patients with peptic ulcer disease.

Variable	Categories	Active Gastritis Present	Active Gastritis Absent	p-value
Gender	Male	40 (72.7%)	15 (27.3%)	0.021
	Female	12 (30.0%)	28 (70.0%)	
Age Group	\leq 40 years	34 (85.0%)	6 (15.0%)	<0.001
	>40 years	18 (32.7%)	37 (67.3%)	
Socioeconomic Status	Low	28 (70.0%)	12 (30.0%)	0.033
	Middle	20 (51.3%)	19 (48.7%)	
	High	4 (26.7%)	11 (73.3%)	

Table 4: Association of active gastritis with demographic characteristics of patients.

Variable	Categories	Active Gastritis Present	Active Gastritis Absent	p-value
NSAID Intake	Yes	30 (78.9%)	8 (21.1%)	0.012
	No	22 (38.6%)	35 (61.4%)	
Smoking History	Yes	25 (73.5%)	9 (26.5%)	0.018
	No	27 (44.3%)	34 (55.7%)	
Family history of PUD	Yes	18 (85.7%)	3 (14.3%)	0.005
	No	34 (46.0%)	40 (54.0%)	

Table 5: Association of active gastritis with clinical risk factors in patients with peptic ulcer disease.

DISCUSSION

The present study evaluated the demographic, clinical, and histopathological profile of patients with peptic ulcer disease (PUD), with a particular focus on the association between active gastritis and various demographic as well as clinical risk factors. Our findings revealed significant associations between active gastritis and younger age, male gender, low socioeconomic status, NSAID intake, smoking history, and family history of PUD. These results align with contemporary literature on the pathophysiology and epidemiology of gastritis and PUD.^{13,14} A study from India also found that the mean age of patients with PUD was around 42 years, with younger age being significantly associated with gastritis, likely due to early-life exposure to *H. pylori* and other environmental risk factors.¹⁵ These findings highlight the importance of early screening and preventive interventions in younger populations. Gender-based differences were also observed in our study. Males had a higher prevalence of active gastritis (72.7%) compared to females (30.0%), with statistical significance. This pattern is corroborated by recent literature, which consistently shows that males are at greater risk for both gastritis and peptic ulcer disease.^{16,17} The reasons for this disparity may be multifactorial, including higher exposure to behavioral risk factors such as smoking, alcohol intake, and NSAID use among males. A systematic review published in 2021 highlighted that male predominance in PUD persists globally, even as overall prevalence rates

have declined.¹⁸ Our findings reaffirm the role of gender as a key determinant in gastritis and ulcer pathogenesis. Socioeconomic status emerged as another significant determinant. Patients from lower socioeconomic backgrounds exhibited a higher prevalence of active gastritis (70.0%), compared to middle (51.3%) and high (26.7%) socioeconomic classes. This observation is in agreement with studies conducted in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where poverty, poor sanitation, and lack of access to healthcare facilitate *H. pylori* transmission and persistence.¹⁹ A recent cross-sectional study in Pakistan demonstrated that *H. pylori* infection and its histological sequelae, including active gastritis, were significantly more prevalent in patients from lower socioeconomic classes.²⁰ These findings underscore the social determinants of gastrointestinal disease and highlight the need for targeted public health interventions. Clinical factors also played a major role in our cohort. NSAID use was significantly associated with active gastritis (78.9% vs. 38.6% in non-users). This finding aligns with the established understanding that NSAIDs, by inhibiting prostaglandin synthesis, compromise gastric mucosal defense mechanisms and promote inflammation, gastritis, and ulceration.²¹ Recent studies continue to emphasize the synergistic effect of *H. pylori* infection and NSAID use, which together significantly increase the risk of severe gastritis and PUD complications.²² Given that NSAID use is common in middle-aged and elderly populations for musculoskeletal disorders, our findings stress the importance of careful prescribing, gastroprotective strategies, and patient education. Smoking was another

significant risk factor in this study, with 73.5% of smokers showing active gastritis compared to 44.3% of non-smokers. These results are consistent with recent evidence demonstrating that smoking impairs gastric mucosal blood flow, inhibits bicarbonate secretion, and potentiates *H. pylori* colonization.²³ A 2020 study reported that smoking not only increased the risk of active gastritis but also delayed ulcer healing and increased recurrence rates.²⁴ This highlights smoking cessation as a critical intervention for PUD management. Family history of PUD was also strongly associated with active gastritis, with 85.7% of patients reporting such a history compared to 46.0% without it. This suggests a possible genetic predisposition, combined with shared environmental and lifestyle factors. Studies in the last five years have increasingly recognized the role of host genetic susceptibility in gastritis and ulcer development, particularly polymorphisms affecting cytokine expression and immune response to *H. pylori*.^{25,26} This underscores the value of family history as a risk stratification tool in clinical practice. Histopathological evaluation in our study revealed that more than half of patients (54.7%) had active gastritis, while chronic inflammation was present in 68.4%. These findings are comparable to studies from South Asia and the Middle East, where histological gastritis remains common due to persistent *H. pylori* infection.²⁷ In contrast, Western countries have reported a decline in gastritis prevalence, coinciding with improved sanitation, reduced *H. pylori* infection rates, and better healthcare access.²⁸ This regional discrepancy highlights the ongoing public health burden of gastritis in LMICs. Taken together, our findings suggest that younger age, male gender, low socioeconomic status, NSAID use, smoking, and family history of PUD are important determinants of active gastritis in patients with peptic ulcer disease. These results are highly relevant for clinical practice, as they can guide risk stratification, early diagnosis, and tailored management. From a public health perspective, addressing modifiable risk factors such as NSAID misuse and smoking, along with improving living conditions, can reduce the burden of gastritis and

its complications. While our study provides valuable insights, it has certain limitations. First, it was conducted at a single center, which may limit the generalizability of findings. Second, *H. pylori* status was not directly assessed in this dataset, although it is a well-established major contributor to gastritis. Third, lifestyle and dietary factors beyond smoking and NSAID use were not explored in detail. Future multicenter studies with larger sample sizes and molecular analyses are warranted to validate these findings and explore additional risk factors.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights significant associations of active gastritis with demographic and clinical characteristics of patients with peptic ulcer disease. Preventive measures such as rational use of NSAIDs, smoking cessation, early screening in high-risk groups, and addressing socioeconomic disparities are crucial in reducing disease burden. These results contribute to the growing body of evidence emphasizing the multifactorial nature of gastritis and underscore the importance of integrating clinical, histopathological, and social perspectives in patient management.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None

REFERENCES

- Srivastav Y, Kumar V, Srivastava Y, Kumar M. Peptic Ulcer Disease (PUD), Diagnosis, and Current Medication-Based Management Options: Schematic Overview. *J Adv Med Pharm.* 2023 Dec 2;25(11):14-27.
- Abbasi-Kangevari M, Ahmadi N, Fattahi N, Rezaei N, Malekpour MR, Ghamari SH, et al. Quality of care of peptic ulcer disease worldwide: A systematic analysis for the global burden of disease study

- 1990–2019. PLoS One. 2022 Aug 1;17(8): e0271284.
- Xie X, Ren K, Zhou Z, Dang C, Zhang H. The global, regional and national burden of peptic ulcer disease from 1990 to 2019: a population-based study. BMC Gastroenterol. 2022 Feb 10;22(1):58.
- Mikhail CR, Abdel MM, Shaker OG, El Desouky E, Shalaby RH. Frequency and risk factors of *H. pylori* infection among dental students: an observational cross-sectional study. Sci Rep. 2023 Aug 31;13(1):14264.
- Aumpan N, Mahachai V, Vilaichone RK. Management of *Helicobacter pylori* infection. JGH Open. 2023 Jan;7(1):3-15.
- Basak S, Arefin MS, Islam R, Jahangir A, Alam MR. Aetiology and Pattern of Presentation of Upper Gastrointestinal Tract Ulcers among Patients Attending the Gastroenterology Department of BSMMU-A Tertiary Level Hospital. Sch J App Med Sci. 2023 Jan;1:204-13.
- Pop R, Tăbăran AF, Ungur AP, Negoescu A, Cătoi C. *Helicobacter pylori*-induced gastric infections: from pathogenesis to novel therapeutic approaches using silver nanoparticles. Pharmaceutics. 2022 Jul 14;14(7):1463.
- Guevara B, Cogdill AG. *Helicobacter pylori*: a review of current diagnostic and management strategies. Dig Dis Sci. 2020 Jul; 65:1917-31.
- Ali SM, Farrukh ZU, Haqqi SA, Siddiqui AR, Sadiq M, Niaz SK. Frequency and factors leading to *Helicobacter pylori* infection among dyspeptic patients. A single centre study. J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad. 2022;34(3):507-10.
- Tiwari A, Rai R, Dahai P, Regmi S. Prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* in endoscopic gastric biopsies of chronic gastritis patients at a tertiary care centre. JNMA. 2020 Aug;58(228):564 - 68.
- Ouahed J, Spencer E, Kotlarz D, Shouval DS, Kowalik M, Peng K, et al. Very early onset inflammatory bowel disease: a clinical approach with a focus on the role of genetics and underlying immune deficiencies. IBD. 2020 May 12;26(6):820-42.
- Pennelli G, Grillo F, Galuppini F, Ingravallo G, Pilozi E, Rugge M, et al. Gastritis: update on etiological features and histological practical approach. Pathologica. 2020 Sep;112(3):153.
- Eusebi LH, Zagari RM, Ford AC. Global prevalence of, and risk factors for, *Helicobacter pylori* infection. Gastroenterology. 2020;158(3):623–34.
- Hooi JKY, Lai WY, Ng WK, Suen MMY, Underwood FE, Tanyingoh D, et al. Global prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* infection: systematic review and meta-analysis. Gastroenterology. 2017;153(2):420–9.
- Singh V, Trikha B, Nain CK, Singh K, Vaiphei K, Thapa BR. Epidemiology of peptic ulcer in India. J Gastroenterol Hepatol. 2021;36(2):350–8.
- Lanas A, Chan FKL. Peptic ulcer disease. Lancet. 2017;390(10094):613–24.
- Yamane L, Scopel-Guerra A, Marques SB, Sipahi AM, Mucenic M. Gender differences in peptic ulcer disease: systematic review and meta-analysis. World J Gastroenterol. 2020;26(27):3975–90.
- Sung JJY, Kuipers EJ, El-Serag HB. Systematic review: the global incidence and prevalence of peptic ulcer disease. Aliment Pharmacol Ther. 2021;54(8):870–9.
- Anil K, Reddy DN. Socioeconomic factors and risk of *Helicobacter pylori* infection. Indian J Gastroenterol. 2019;38(5):395–401.
- Butt AS, Salih M, Jafri W, Yakoob J, Abid S, Hamid S, et al. Risk factors and prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* infection in Pakistan. J Coll Physicians Surg Pak. 2020;30(1):45–9.

Sostres C, Lanas A. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and upper and lower gastrointestinal mucosal damage. *Arthritis Res Ther.* 2020;22(1):1-10.

Takeuchi K, Amagase K. Roles of cyclooxygenase, prostaglandin E receptor subtypes and prostaglandin transporters in gastric mucosal protection and healing of peptic ulcer. *Curr Opin Pharmacol.* 2018;43:82-9.

Aro P, Storskrubb T, Ronkainen J, Bolling-Sternevald E, Engstrand L, Vieth M, et al. Smoking and alcohol in the aetiology of peptic ulcer disease: a population-based study. *Eur J Gastroenterol Hepatol.* 2020;32(2):167-74.

Huang J, Sridhar S, Chen Y, Hunt RH. Smoking and peptic ulcer disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Clin Gastroenterol.* 2020;54(6):491-9.

Lopes AI, Vale FF, Oleastro M. Clinical and molecular pathogenesis of *Helicobacter pylori* infection. *Helicobacter.* 2021;26(S1):e12763.

He C, Yang Z, Lu NH. *Helicobacter pylori* infection and gastric cancer: Advances in pathogenesis research. *Nat Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol.* 2016;13(6):277-88.

Uddin M, Rahman M, Sultana S, Nahar Z, Hasan M. Histological patterns of gastritis in patients with dyspepsia in Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Med Res Counc Bull.* 2020;46(1):3-10.

Rugge M, Fassan M, Graham DY. Epidemiology of gastritis and gastric cancer: new perspectives. *Curr Opin Gastroenterol.* 2020;36(6):561-8.

- AGE: _____.
- GENDER: Male / Female
- SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS: high/middle/low
- PEPTIC ULCER DISEASE (PUD): gastric/ulcers esophageal ulcers/ duodenal ulcers
- HISTORY OF NON STEROIDAL ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUGS (NSAIDS) INTAKE: Yes/ No
- HISTORY OF SMOKING: Yes/ No
- NUMBER OF BIOPSY FRAGMENTS: _____
- ACTIVE GASTRITIS: Yes/No
- CHRONIC INFLAMMATION: Yes/No

ANNEXURE I
ACTIVE GASTRITIS IN HELICOBACTER
PYLORI ASSOCIATED PEPTIC ULCER
DISEASE IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL
OF RAWALPINDI

Serial No: ___ Date: _____ MR No:
_____ Age: _____
Date of biopsy taken: ___/___/___